

A STUDY ON CONSUMERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ORGANIC PRODUCTS

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Abstract:

A well-balanced diet with enough of nutrients is essential, which can be obtained from organic foods. Organic foods are more nutrient-dense and high in anti-oxidants, and they can help with a variety of ailments. A sample of 100 respondents was randomly collected from various consumers through online survey. The collected data has been analysed using statistical tools such as simple percentage, chi-square test and friedman ranking test. The research concluded that consumers' attitude strongly impacts their preferences for organic products to lead a healthy and wealthy life.

Key Words: Organic Products, Health, Attitude, Preference, Balanced, Diet, Essential, Etc

Introduction:

Sustainability is regarded as the most critical public health concern in the twenty-first century. Because consumer choices about the environment have an impact on the quality of life and health of future and present generations, the task of establishing healthier communities begins with environmental awareness and the coordinated implementation of eco-friendly behaviour. In the current situation, the desire to create a healthy and sustainable environment has piqued the interest of academics, corporations, the media, government, and non-governmental groups in environmental issues. The gravity of these challenges has prompted consumers to become more aware of their consumption habits, resulting in the green movement, practices and actions. A person who is environmentally conscious will promote a healthier lifestyle.

In the 1950s, India faced food scarcity as a result of population growth and natural calamities. To combat this, the Green Revolution was launched in the 1960s, which increased agricultural production by introducing high-yielding variety seeds, as well as fertilizers and pesticides. Pesticides can cause a variety of health problems in humans, ranging from headaches to chronic diseases such as cancer. Even a small amount of pesticide exposure in the environment produces long-term health impacts. Cancer is responsible for one out of every eight deaths worldwide, making it a global epidemic. By 2030, the cancer burden is expected to rise to 21.7 million cases and 13 million deaths if current trends continue (American Cancer Society). Cancer claims the lives of 7 lakhs individuals every year in India. In future million new cases reported every year it is anticipated to increase fivefold by 2025.

Diseases is caused by both internal factors such as hormones and a weakened immune system, as well as external factors such as industrialization, food habits, lifestyle, and population expansion. Poor diet is clearly identified in the literature as a risk factor for greater chronic illness occurrence. As a result, understanding the importance of a well-balanced diet is critical for good health. India's health-care system is excellent, and it is expected to improve much further in the future. Rather than establishing a health-care system, one should focus on preventing diseases. Prevention is preferable to cure. As a result, staying healthy requires avoiding illness through numerous prevention strategies. The most effective way is to change one's eating habits.

A well-balanced diet with enough of nutrients is essential, which can be obtained from organic foods. Organic foods are more nutrient-dense and high in anti-oxidants, and they can help with a variety of ailments. When it comes to organic food, India is riddled with contradictions. On the one hand, it is becoming a major player in the worldwide market, notably in Europe; on the other hand, the organic food sector in the United States is still in its infancy. India began exporting tea to Europe in the early 1990s and formed its first joint venture with German organic food companies. Currently, approximately 300 goods are available in roughly 20 different product categories. Tea, fruit, corn, grains, vegetables, spices, and completed products, as well as organic cotton, are some of them. More than 40% of the items are sent to Europe, with Canada, the United States, Australia, New Zealand, Japan, Switzerland, and Korea as other trading partners.

Review of Literature:

Dr. H. M. Chandrashekar (2014) examined the main problems of organic consumers are irregular vacuity of organic products. Occasionally, the organic consumer would buy non organic products along with organic products. The organic products are too precious than non-organic products. So that the organic consumers aren't to coping further volume of products. The kinds of organic products which are available in the request are limited, there's a lack of mindfulness about organic products to consumers.

Dr. NilimaVarma (2016) observed that mindfulness of food markers shows that repliers weren't veritably apprehensive with organic food markers. Results indicated that the main reasons for coping organic food products are an anticipation of a healthier and environmentally friendly means of product. The study plant that the groups of buyers and non buyers have significant differences in demographic characteristics.

S. Amudha, and Dr. M. Kanagarathinam (2017) revealed that organic food refers to crops or beast that are grown on the ranch without the operation of synthetic diseases or fungicides, and without using genetically modified organisms. The organic food assiduity is fairly small and new, it's important that consumer's come apprehensive of its claims, limitations, and implicit benefits. The main end of the study is to find out the consumer's mindfulness towards the organic food products and safety of the yield that they buy in stores due to possible fungicide impurity. For this purpose a well – structured check of 550 repliers covering the Coimbatore megacity was taken and suitable statistical tools have been used for analysis. The exploration concludes that utmost of the repliers have high position of mindfulness towards organic products.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the consumers attitude towards organic products.
- To analyze the factors influencing consumer attitude towards organic food products.

Research Methodology:

Primary data is collected through well-structured questionnaire through online survey. A sample of 100 consumers has been collected using random sampling method. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. Secondary data has been collected through journals, magazines, websites, books, etc., For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- Simple Percentage
- Chi-Square Test
- Friedman Ranking test.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is restricted to the selected sample through online survey and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Consumers

Factors	Number of Consumers N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	63	63
Female	37	37
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	14	14
26 to 50	57	57
Above 50	29	29
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	68	68
Graduate	21	21
House wife	11	11
Annual Income		
Up to Rs.1,00,000	24	24
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	34	34
Above Rs.2,50,000	42	42
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	36	36
Joint Family	64	64
Sources of Knowledge		
Friends/ Relatives	61	61
Mass Media	12	12
Officers	27	27
Organic Products		
Medicines	13	13
Cosmetics	20	20
Home Products	12	12

Organic Vegetables and Fruits	33	33
Milk and Milk Products	12	12
Cereals and Pulses	10	10

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the consumers for the study. Out of 100 consumers who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (63%) of the consumers are male, (57%) whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most (68%) of the consumers are graduates, the Annual income of (42%) consumers is above Rs.2,50,000, (64%) of the consumers belong to nuclear family, (61%) of the consumers came to know about the organic products through Friends/Relatives and (33%) of the consumers buy organic vegetables and fruits.

Table 2: Relationship between the Demographic Profile and level of attitude towards organic products

Factors	Level of Attitude			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
	Low	Moderate	High				
Gender							
Male	13	22	38	63	8.537	5.991	S
Female	8	13	16	37			
Age (Years)							
Up to 25	4	5	5	14	4.539	9.488	NS
26 to 50	17	26	14	57			
Above 50	12	5	12	29			
Educational Qualification							
Up to School Level	26	20	22	68	12.2683	9.488	S
Graduate	8	8	5	21			
House wife	4	3	4	11			
Annual Income							
Up to Rs.1,00,000	11	7	6	24	7.823	9.488	NS
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	9	19	6	34			
Above Rs.2,50,000	14	18	10	42			
Type of Family							
Nuclear Family	7	20	9	36	4.698	5.991	NS
Joint Family	18	34	12	64			
Sources of Knowledge							
Friends/ Relatives	11	23	27	61	13.564	9.488	S
Mass Media	3	5	4	12			
Officers	10	7	10	27			

*significant at 5% percent level

Table 2 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables and Level of the attitude of the consumers. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exist any significant association between age, annual income, type of family of the consumers and level of attitude towards organic products. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between gender, educational qualification of the consumers, source of knowledge about organic products and level of attitude towards organic products. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Attitude of consumers towards Organic Products– Friedman Rank Test

Factors	SA	A	NANDA	DA	SDA	Total	Average Rank	Rank
Harmless	22.40	63.60	9.80	4.10	0.00	100	5.26	1
Fresher	13.04	45.08	37.76	2.29	1.83	100	4.05	6
Natural	16.02	55.38	25.40	2.29	0.92	100	4.69	3
No Pesticides	15.10	51.03	29.29	3.89	0.69	100	4.36	5
Healthy	25.63	55.38	16.02	2.52	0.46	100	5.24	2
Nutritious	19.45	45.08	30.89	3.66	0.92	100	4.46	4
Quality	14.70	42.79	25.63	13.50	3.48	100	3.95	7
Taste	13.96	39.59	36.61	7.32	2.52	100	3.88	8

Table no.3 shows about the Friedman Rank Test for level of attitude of consumers towards organic products were 0.000 level of significance which shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. It shows that Harmless was the first level of attitude factor of the consumers to choose the organic products. Healthy was ranked as the second factor to choose the organic products natural was ranked as third factor, Nutritious was ranked as fourth factor, No Pesticides was the fifth factor, Fresher and Quality was the sixth factor and Taste was the seventh factor which was preferred by the consumers to choose the organic products.

From the Friedman rank test it is found that majority of the consumers prefer Harmless and Healthy organic products and the like.

Conclusion:

The quantitative disquisition epitomized that attitude of consumer's strongly determine their preferences for organic, conventional and conventional plus products. Consumer attitude tended to differ further between organic product choices rather than conventional choices. The study also concluding that occasional organic consumers were eclectic in their priorities. To conclude, specific fresh benefits of organic husbandry should be communicated in clear and catchy dispatches. Besides this, it's important to strengthen affirmative consumer attitude towards organic product and farther trouble should be put into pressing and adding the attractiveness of organic products. Policy support should concentrate on adding the domestic and indigenous force of organic products. This could be achieved by means of strengthening networks, minimizing profitable trouble and creating impulses for conversion to organic husbandry. Likewise, it's important to give know- style and to meliorate organic farmers 'entrepreneurial chops in order to increase organic estate intrushes. Consumers have advanced prospects of organic than they do of conventional food in terms of origin and of the food country miles travelled between the place of product and the point of trade. Consumers' attitude strongly impacts their preferences for organic products to lead a healthy and wealthy life.

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